

FATIGUE AND STRESS OF PHYSICS TEACHERS IN THE CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the fatigue of teachers who teach Physical Science in the first grade of high school in Greece. Twenty secondary school physics teachers aged 40-50 who teach first grade during the last two hours of the program participated in the study. From the research, important conclusions can be recorded that are related to the teaching and the way in which the students participate in the last hours of the weekly program. Teachers feel tired in the last hours and it seems that it is difficult to teach physical science. They do not have the ability and time to do laboratory experiments with the students and also the students are very tired in the last two hours. It turns out that they would like more hours of physics in the weekly schedule for the first grade and think that it is difficult for the students to pay attention to the physics lesson. Also in the last hours many students leave the school. The research showed that it is much better to have physics lessons in the first hours of the school schedule rather than the last hours, also to have more time in the first grade for the physics lesson so that the teachers can use laboratory experiments with the students and have more time for teaching.

Key Words: Physics, Teaching Fatigue, Educators, Curriculum

Introduction

Through the process of generating ideas and discovering methods that the student can be led to discover in the physics lesson, we must examine modern teaching methods.

But for this to become a reality not only for students but also for teachers there should be the appropriate tools and practices that give the student the opportunity to discover new knowledge in every educational hour in the classroom (Schizas, D., & Psillos, D., 2019).

We know very well that physical science can combine many more lessons and even to give additional explanations in to different daily problems. For this reason physics we could say that is a holistic science and in a spirit of cooperation with many other lessons taught at school.

One of the important tools of teaching physics in the classroom is to make connections of physical science with reality and its application in everyday life. (Jones, A.T., Kirk, C.M., 1989)

In order to do this, students should spend many hours in laboratory experiments where they will be able to understand physics and applications and be able to have conclusions more easily.

With this method they will be able to connect theory with practice and better understand the phenomena of Physics and its Laws. They will also be able to participate more effectively in

the lesson with questions and answers. This can give them the opportunity to love the lesson more and to follow with more ease without feeling bored.

Natural science is based on and analyzed through observation and experiment. Through these two and by using mathematical formulas the laws and the phenomena of physical science become easier especially to young children in school (Christian Tarchi, 2014).

Theoretical Problems in Learning Physics

Students today are facing very big innovative technological changes so they think in a different way. So many of the lessons taught in school today do not seem very important to them. In their daily life they find different problems than those children had about ten years ago (Olalekan Taofeek Badmus, Loyiso C. Jita, 2022)

One problem that exists in the school's curriculum is the large number of different lessons, many of which are theoretical and refer to the main language, philosophy, history, and lessons that are not so similar to the Physics Science (Ravanis K., 2003). During the daily program in the school unit, especially in the first hours of the program, the students get tired watching and participating in various lessons which most of them do not have any direct application in to the today's modern environment.(Shaila Banu , 2011).

So they get tired and in the last hours of the program they are not able to attend and to be more focused in to Teacher's teaching.

It is also very important to look more closely at the daily schedule of the different lessons so students will have the possibility to combine knowledge and different ideas of learning during the same day at the school(Katsijkas X.& Kavadias G.2002)). This of course gives us the possibility to think of other more modern methods of teaching, different than the ones we apply today.

This is very important because in this way we give the opportunity to our students to be more interesting to learn until the last hours of the program in the school.(Nott M. and Wellington J. 1998).

It is very important to note that in the Greek school there is not enough time for experiments. Of course there are laboratories, but it is not possible to do experiments with a total number of teaching hours of Physics only two a week for the first grade of high school.

The Research Method

For the research were selected high school Physics Teachers from Greece who voluntarily and anonymously participated in the research completing the questionnaires given to them from the first week.

This paper refers to a research in a group of 20 Physics Teachers with ages between 40-50 years old who teach in public and private schools in Greece. Teachers had a daily program teaching no more than of 4 to 5 hours of classes on the same day.

The teachers, most of them 12 teach in public schools and 8 in private classes. All the twenty teachers returned completed questionnaires in three weeks. The research was done during the last three weeks of the month of November when approximately two months have passed since the beginning of the educational school year.

The main direction of the research was in the attempt to study the fatigue of the teachers during the last two hours of the educational program in the school in the first grade classes of a high school.

The direction of the research was to record the problems that arise in relation to the fatigue of teachers in secondary education at the high school (Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K., 2011). This research specialized in the physics lesson in the last hours of the program.

In this direction for the research, a questionnaire was created to investigate the fatigue of teachers and students behavior in order to combine and extract important results. With this questionnaire, we tried to record the fatigue of the teachers and to study the factors that influence and increase it in relation to the physics lesson.

The research questionnaire given to the Teachers at the beginning and asked them to return the answers after three weeks.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire consisted of ten questions which are shown below from 1 to 10 total.

Questions

Q1. How many hours a week do you teach first grade physics?

Q2. How many students usually study in every class?

10-15, 16-20, 20-25

Q3. How tired you feel during the last two hours of the program?

Very low, Low, a lot, Too Much

Q4. What is the level you perform in Physics class in the last two hours?

Very low, low, A lot, Too Much

Q5. How much do you think your students have watch your teachings in the last two hours?

Very low, low, A lot, Too Much

Q6. If you present experiments to your students you think that would follow with more interest,

Same, More, Much, Too Much

Q7. On average, how many students leave school in the last two hours,

1-2, 3-5, more than 5

Q8. Would you prefer to discuss some Physics topic with the students in the last hours. Maybe, maybe not, I don't know

Q9. You think that you would be more effective in teaching if you had a physics class in the first hours of the curriculum?

Maybe, Yes, Definitely yes, I don't know

Q10. What is your suggestion for the maximum number of teaching hours in the first grade?

Each week, Two, Three, Four

The answers we received as they appear in the TABLE 1

Q1	An	2						
Q2	An	10-15: 0,	15-20:4,	20-25:16				
Q3	An	Very low: 0,	Low: 0,	A lot: 12,	Too Much: 8			
Q4	An	Very low: 0,	Low: 14,	A lot: 6,	Too Much: 0			
Q5	An	Very law: 3,	law: 16,	A lot: 1,	Too Much: 0			
Q6	An	Same: 9,	More: 10,	Much: 1,	Too Much: 0			
Q7	An	1-2: 8,	3-5:12,	More than 5: 0				
Q8	An	Maybe: 14,	May be not: 6,	I don't know: 0				
Q9	An	Maybe: 0,	Yes: 0,	Definitely yes: 20,	I don't know: 0			
Q10	An	Two: 0,	Three: 2	Four: 18				

TABLE 1 Number of Question and Answers

In the following TABLE 2 appear the % total per answer

	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%
Q1	2	100						
Q2	0	0	4	20	16	80		
Q3	0	0	0	0	12	60	8	40
Q4	0	0	14	70	6	30	0	0
Q5	3	15	16	80	1	5	0	0
Q6	9	45	10	50	1	5	0	0
Q7	8	40	12	60	0	0		
Q8	14	70	6	30	0	0		
Q9	0	0	0	0	20	100	0	0
Q10	0	0	2	10	18	90		

TABLE 2 The % total number per answer

Questions about stress of the Teachers in the last two hours of teaching

Please put **X** in the place you think is near correct for You

1. Is your stress from the beginning of the daily program in your school

Small	Medium	Large
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2. Is your stress in the middle of the program

Small	Medium	Large
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3. Is your stress in the last hours of the program

Small	Medium	Large
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The answers we received are as they appear in the TABLE 3

Question	Small	%	Medium	%	Large	%
Q1	2	10	14	70	4	20
Q2	5	20	9	45	6	30
Q3	2	10	2	10	16	80

TABLE 3 TOTAL ANSWERS AND % PER QUESTION

Statistical Results and research information

The answers of the Questionnaire inducted in the diagrams for every question

Fig 1 Diagram for Answers of the Question 2

Fig 2 Diagram for Answers of the Question 3

Fig 3 Diagram for Answers of the Question 4

Fig 4 Diagram for Answers of the Question 5

Fig 5 Diagram for Answers of the Question6

Fig 6 Diagram for Answers of the Question 7

Fig 7 Diagram for Answers of the Question 8

Fig 8 Diagram for Answers of the Question 9

Fig 9 Diagram for Answers of the Question 10

Statistical analysis diagram of the Stress Questions

Fig 10 Diagram for Answers of the Questions for Stress

General Information and Proposals

It is very important to see the results from this research. Among the very important conclusions that emerge is that the teachers feel tired from the indifference of the students and also from the long hours of teaching. We also see that the students do not have the same desire to attend the Physics lesson in the last hours of the school schedule. It is also important that the teachers consider that the two hours in the program for the first grade of high school are not enough to help students understand and learn Physics.

Teachers feel tired in the last hours and it seems that it is difficult to teach physical science. They do not have the ability and time to do laboratory experiments with the students and also the students are very tired in the last two hours. It turns out that they would like more hours of physics in the weekly schedule for the first grade and think that it is difficult for the students to pay attention to the physics lesson. Also in the last hours many students leave the school.

The research showed that it is much better to have physics lessons in the first hours of the school schedule rather than the last hours, also to have more time in the first grade for the physics lesson so that the teachers can use laboratory experiments with the students and have more time for teaching (Eugenia Etkina, Aaron Warren, and Michael Gentile, 2006).

To make it more meaningful, students must be able to understand the mathematical relationship that exists behind every law of physics and must be able to connect physical facts, laws and phenomena to be able to find conclusions.

In the first class there were students who spoke the same mother language and some students no more than 5 in each class who spoke at least one different language.

Teachers were often forced to explain the phenomena and the laws of physics in two languages, Greek and English. This method of teaching created an additional problem for the students because many students were not able to understand the second language well. This may be the case with students who could not attend the lesson that was taught in the main spoken language of instruction (Lena Hansson and Lotta Leden 2016).

From the answers and the percentages from the analysis of the answers about stress, it seems that the teachers report significant stress in the first hours of the lessons. This is probably due to the start of classes and may be related to the restlessness of the students in the first hours upon entering the school.

It is also important to note that in the last hours the teachers also show a significant amount of stress. This may be due to the indifference of the students in the last hours of the program and especially in a difficult course, which is the Physics lesson. This should be taken seriously so that changes are made to the course schedule in the future.

Special emphasis must be given to the Physics lessons and the hours that will be taught so that students can reach the lesson from previous easier lessons. This will rest the students and help the teachers to better organize their lesson with less work stress in a difficult school schedule.

This, according to the teachers, created additional mental fatigue especially when the lessons were held in the last hours of the curriculum. It would be very important not to have classes with students who speak two different languages in the same course but for the education system to try to help students who do not speak the language of the host country to initially do enough preparatory courses to help them understand more of physics lessons, or to have lessons for these students at different times until they learn to speak and write the second language.

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